

ISLAMIC BANKING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR REDUCING SOCIAL INEQUALITY: THE CASE OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of Islamic banking as a tool for reducing social inequality, using Bosnia and Herzegovina as a case study. The Balkan region has increasingly been targeted by investments from the GCC region, including Bosnia Bank International (BBI) as one of those investments, recognized as the only Islamic bank in the region. Islamic banking is a form of moral banking, aimed at profit maximization without compromising ethical standards. These ethical norms are critical in shaping business operations, wherein Islamic banks are expected not only to be profitable but to positively contribute to societal welfare, particularly in addressing disparities between the rich and the poor. By adhering to the principles of socially responsible banking, grounded in justice, solidarity, and the prohibition of harmful economic activities, Islamic banking offers an alternative financial model with considerable potential for reducing social inequalities. This paper analyzes the role of BBI, its implementation of Islamic financial instruments, and the impact of various projects that have contributed to reducing social disparities in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Islamic financial instruments, being partnership-based, are hypothesized to foster greater equity in relationships between banks and clients. Projects such as the Sarajevo Business Forum, Sarajevo Halal Fair, credit lines with Cantonal and Municipal authorities, zero-margin financial lines for clients, and student scholarship programs organized by the Bank demonstrate BBI's substantial engagement in social responsibility, surpassing the efforts of conventional banks. This suggests that BBI's operations reflect a deeper commitment to addressing social vulnerability and promoting social justice compared to traditional banks. The study also explores the challenges BBI faces and considers the potential for further development of Islamic financial institutions within the region. The findings suggest that Islamic banking, through institutions such as BBI, can offer sustainable solutions to both economic and social challenges, fostering a more equitable distribution of resources and promoting social inclusion. Islamic banking not only operates through financial instruments but also contributes to community welfare through

non-banking activities that have a measurable impact on reducing social inequalities. Furthermore, the study examines how Islamic banks like BBI can serve as catalysts for broader economic change, including promoting entrepreneurship and job creation. Ultimately, this research emphasizes the potential of these models to inspire the development of other socially responsible financial institutions across the wider Balkan region.

Keywords: Islamic banking, social inequality, Bosnia Bank International (BBI), Socially responsible banking, financial instruments, social welfare.

INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has seen significant growth over the past few decades, largely driven by societal demands for corporations to address social inequality. Factors such as global market dynamics, decentralized management structures, ethical crises, scandals, and growing social inequality have all fueled this expansion. Society increasingly expects companies, particularly financial institutions, to be more socially responsible and contribute to societal welfare (Mohammed, 2007). As Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) continues to gain traction, Islamic banking and finance are also witnessing significant growth. The Islamic financial sector, according to a 2022 report from ICD and Refinitiv, has reached a substantial 4 trillion USD in total assets and is growing at an annual rate of approximately 7-8%. Since Islamic financial institutions are guided by Shari'ah law, which seeks to benefit all aspects of human life and minimize harm, these institutions are expected to prioritize CSR more than their conventional counterparts. Dusuki and Abdullah (2007) argue that Islamic financial institutions should lead in CSR initiatives and work towards reducing social inequality.

Islamic banks, bound by Shari'ah, incorporate ethical principles into their operations, making them distinct from conventional banks (Kahf, 1999). Some critics argue that there are no significant differences between IFI and commercial institutions when it comes to CSR implementation which is proved in the example of Malaysia (Chong and Liu, 2010). Following the theory, Islamic banks should follow ethical and moral principles before profitability, differentiating them from conventional approaches. Islamic banks, rooted in Islamic values, should focus on reducing the wealth gap through numerous projects (Basah and Yusuf, 2013).

In practice, however, the distinction between Islamic and conventional banks is often blurred. Both types of banks implement CSR projects and use them as a tool to attract customers. The issue arises when CSR becomes merely a marketing strategy aimed at profit maximization (Tran, 2014). This profit-driven behavior is evident in the financing models used by Islamic banks, where most profits are generated from loan-based financing rather than equity-based models. While it is generally acknowledged that Islamic banking has a stronger focus on socially vulnerable groups compared to conventional banking, this has not been consistently reflected in implementation strategies. The study referenced by Basah and Yusuf (2013) represents a critical step in assessing the actual contribution of Islamic banks to reducing social inequality.

According to estimates from the Central Bank of Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H) in its 2023 Annual Report, modest economic growth is anticipated in 2024 due to ongoing inflationary pressures and limited trade opportunities for domestic industrial

production and exports. These challenges characterized 2023, particularly the decline in external demand. This downturn was attributed to deteriorating monetary conditions and high inflation. Key factors for Bosnia's GDP growth in 2023 included increased investment spending, both public and private, as well as rising wages and employment levels (Barašin, 2024).

There is only one Islamic bank operating in the South-East Europe region – Bosnia Bank International, and it was established and founded by the strongest Islamic banks in UAE and KSA. BBI has played a significant role in CSR initiatives in Bosnia, aiming to support disadvantaged communities (BBI, 2024). These CSR efforts can be categorized into two types: business-oriented projects such as credit lines and investment conferences, and charitable activities like scholarships, humanitarian aid, and other community-focused projects. Both categories will be explored and analyzed in this study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main goals of the research paper are CSR-based initiatives that IFI implemented in Bosnia and Herzegovina in order to reduce the gap between rich and poor. This means that the study will be focused on Bosnia Bank International (BBI) as the only Islamic bank in B&H. As mentioned above, BBI has been undertaking two categories of these projects: projects which are the part of business portfolio such as Sarajevo Business Forum, credit lines with official authorities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Turkish credit line, Al-Maktoum fund, and IDB trust fund. The second category of projects is those based on charity activities such as student scholarships and humanitarian work.

The research involves a qualitative analysis of available data on CSR initiatives within Bosnia and Herzegovina's banking sector, focusing on the role of Islamic banks in reducing social inequality. The analysis explains the main CSR projects initiated by BBI with a significant impact on reducing social inequality. Data sources consist of official reports from BBI.

SOCIAL INEQUALITY IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Central Bank's 2023 Annual Report projects modest economic growth for 2024. This restrained outlook is attributed mainly to persistent high inflation and limited trade prospects for both domestic industrial production and exports. These issues marked the entire year of 2023, particularly the decline in external demand. The decrease in external demand followed the deterioration of monetary conditions and high inflationary pressures. The key assumptions for domestic GDP growth in 2023 are the growth of investment spending (personal and government), accompanied by an increase in nominal wages and employment. The growth of private sector investments is influenced by still lower domestic interest rates compared to those in the eurozone and retained financial profit from the previous year, in which many companies recorded record net profits. An increase in government investment spending is expected, driven by work on large infrastructure projects, which can be especially anticipated in 2024 due to local elections. For 2024, a GDP

growth rate of 2.1% is projected, assuming a weakening of inflationary trends, and it is expected that inflation will be significantly lower during this year hitting 3% (Barašin, 2024). According to Tutnjić (2022), around 70% of citizens in Bosnia and Herzegovina today are in the poverty zone, with 30% of them lacking even the basics for a "bare existence," surviving due to help from public kitchens. The main reasons for the situations are various, starting from the consequences of the war and the transition process, exposing the population to new types of risks such as recession, rising unemployment, and inflation.

One of the main issues that society faces today is the problem of social inequality, with wealth disparity being a dominant factor. In modern societies, the number of people living in poverty is steadily growing, while wealth and power stay in the hands of 1 percent of the world population.

According to some authors, less than 10% of the population controls more than 90% of the total wealth. This situation leaves a large portion of society feeling dissatisfied and frustrated with the current state of affairs. For these discontented members, democratic processes provide a way to push for changes in how society operates, seeking to create a system that better serves their needs (Plojović, Bećirović, Plojović, and Ujkanović, 2018).

The significant difference between rich and poor is an issue affecting people's lives around the world and especially in Bosnia and Herzegovina which is still recovering from war consequences from 90's. Different regions get access to resources in different ways, and there's a clear gap in things like education, jobs, and healthcare. The unemployment rate hovers around 15.7%, but for young people, it's much worse, sitting at about 40%. Ethnic divisions between Bosniaks, Croats, and Serbs also play a role in how unequal things are. In rural areas, poverty rates are significantly higher, with nearly 50% of people struggling to make ends meet, compared to around 20% in urban areas. Many young people are leaving the country, with more than 50,000 emigrating each year in search of better opportunities. The country should deal with the issue of inequality in order to transform into a well-developed country (Barašin, 2024).

Islamic Banking in Bosnia and Herzegovina

There were initiatives to develop Islamic finance in Yugoslavia starting in the early 1990s, intending to strengthen ties between the former Yugoslav region and Iran. However, these initiatives were quickly halted with the onset of war in the 1990s (Hadžić, 2014).

The first chance to establish IFI in Bosnia and Herzegovina involved Vakuf Bank and it was not successful. The only IFI operating in the SEE region is Bosnia Bank International.

BBI has been the fastest-growing bank in B&H generating 7-8% annual growth, but still having modest market share at 5%. Since it was established, it has focused on Islamic finance development and CSR projects, especially under the management of Amer Bukvic, the creator of Sarajevo Business Forum. Nowadays, BBI faces administrative changes and it is going to be interesting to analyze their impact on Islamic finance development in the future. Additionally, BBI has implemented other

corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives, including student scholarships, BBI Academy, and the BBI VIP Business Club, with the goal of educating the public about Islamic banking principles and connecting clients (Bosnia Bank International, 2024). BBI's total assets grew from 144 million BAM in 2006 to 1.49 billion BAM by the end of 2021. In 2023, BBI Bank achieved outstanding results with above-average market share growth in terms of profitability and strategic client segments, recording a net profit of 23.3 million BAM, a 59% increase compared to the same period the previous year (Bosnia Bank International, 2024).

BBI PROJECTS FOR REDUCING SOCIAL INEQUALITY IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

The earliest attempts to establish a domestic bank under Islamic law in the former Yugoslavia began in the early 1990s, with plans to create the region's first Islamic bank to foster economic growth and strengthen ties. As discussed previously, BBI has been implementing many CSR projects in order to bring benefits to society. These initiatives fall into two main categories: projects within BBI's business portfolio and those focused on charitable and humanitarian efforts.

The first category includes credit-financing partnerships with local municipalities and authorities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Turkish credit line, the Al-Maktoum fund, and the IDB trust fund. The second category includes projects as follows: Sarajevo Business Forum, student scholarships, and other projects that are not part of core banking activities. The mentioned projects will be analyzed in the following chapters.

BBI's Banking Projects Implemented with the Goal of Reducing Social Inequality

The financing lines set up with municipalities and cantonal governments in Bosnia and Herzegovina, totaling around 400 million BAM with very low profit margins of 0% to 2%, have really helped in reducing social inequality. By offering affordable funding, they've given small and medium-sized businesses a chance to grow, create jobs, and improve living standards, especially in areas that are often overlooked. This has helped level the playing field between rural and urban regions, giving more people access to opportunities they might not have had otherwise. These funds have also supported key sectors like agriculture and manufacturing, helping more people from different backgrounds get involved in the economy, which has made a real difference in narrowing the gap between the rich and the poor. The lines were implemented with Sarajevo and Tuzla Cantons in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, and municipalities of Sarajevo city such as Stari grad, Ilidža, Novo Sarajevo, and Novi Grad. These governmental authorities have subsidized the profit margin for small and medium-sized enterprises, reducing it sometimes to 0%, and at most to 2% (Bosnia Bank International, 2024).

The next project implemented by BBI Bank was the Turkish financing line. According to Zogić, Nicević, and Meta (2024) the Turkish credit line, handled by BBI Bank, has made a real difference in the lives of many people in Bosnia and Herzegovina. With a total of 249 million BAM provided, this line of credit has been a lifeline for small

and medium-sized businesses, especially in sectors like agriculture. According to BBI Bank, this initiative has led to the creation of 2,830 new jobs and helped engage 1,481 contractors, which means thousands of families now have a more stable income. What's even more important is how this credit line has helped reduce social inequality. Lowering interest rates in agriculture, an industry that employs a lot of people in rural and poorer areas, has made it easier for farmers and small businesses to access the funds they need. With lower borrowing costs, they've been able to buy new equipment, grow their operations, and become more productive. This kind of support helps rural communities, where opportunities are often limited, and brings them closer to the level of urban areas.

The IDB Trust Fund and the Al-Maktoum Fund have channeled over 4 million KM to support the returnee population in Bosnia and Herzegovina. These contributions have had a profound effect on improving the economic landscape, particularly in regions still recovering from the war. Through financial aid, returnees have been able to rebuild their homes, start small businesses, and access vital resources they otherwise wouldn't have had. This support has led to the creation of jobs and breathed life back into local economies, giving many families a renewed sense of hope and stability.

Beyond just financial support, these funds have played a significant role in fostering social stability. By empowering returnees to become self-sufficient, they have reduced the need for ongoing humanitarian aid, allowing people to stand on their own feet. This economic boost has helped integrate marginalized communities back into the mainstream economy, promoting unity and social cohesion. The assistance from the IDB Trust Fund and the Al-Maktoum Fund has not only transformed the lives of countless returnees but also contributed to the long-term recovery and development of Bosnia and Herzegovina as a whole (Bosnia Bank International, 2024).

BBI's Non-Banking Projects Implemented with the Goal of Reducing Social Inequality

As it is mentioned on the official website of BBI: "Bosnia Bank International, alongside its shareholders and many local and international partners, organizes the annual Sarajevo Business Forum, an international conference focused on business and investment. Since its first event in 2010, the forum has established itself as one of the leading business and investment gatherings in Southeast Europe. The Sarajevo Business Forum serves as an event where project authors and potential investors meet in order to seek business opportunities.

The conference facilitates networking and helps explore new business and investment opportunities in the region, with the core mission of promoting economic development throughout Southeast Europe. Over the years, the forum has attracted many important and influential political and economic leaders from many countries and companies.

The Sarajevo Business Forum has been instrumental in positioning Bosnia and Herzegovina as a rising destination for international investment. Through the forum, numerous opportunities in key sectors such as energy, tourism, agriculture, and infrastructure are brought to the attention of foreign investors, revealing the country's

vast economic potential. The discussions and connections forged during the event have led to significant investments, driving job creation, technology advancement, and overall economic progress in the region. By fostering partnerships between local businesses and international investors, the forum has helped integrate Bosnia and Herzegovina more deeply into global markets. The exposure to foreign capital and expertise has been invaluable for the country's growth, allowing it to better tap into international resources. Over time, Sarajevo Business Forum has become not just a hub for foreign direct investment but also a key driver of Bosnia and Herzegovina's evolving role in the economic landscape of Southeast Europe (Bosnia Bank International, 2024).

The second very significant project to mention is the Salih Kamil Fund, which has provided scholarships to more than 500 students. These scholarships are specially designed to help children who have lost one or both parents, focusing on those who are in the greatest need. By offering financial support, the fund gives these young people the chance to pursue their education, something that might not have been possible given their difficult circumstances. This initiative is more than just financial aid—it's a lifeline that brings hope, stability, and the opportunity for a brighter future for some of the most vulnerable members of society (Bosnia Bank International, 2024).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research highlights the significant potential of Islamic banking as an effective tool for reducing social inequality, with a focus on Bosnia and Herzegovina. The case of Bosnia Bank International (BBI) showcases how Islamic banking, rooted in ethical principles and social responsibility, goes beyond traditional financial services to make a tangible impact on marginalized communities. BBI's various initiatives, such as affordable credit lines, strategic investment projects, and scholarship programs, demonstrate how these efforts contribute to improving the economic conditions for vulnerable populations, particularly in regions still recovering from the aftermath of conflict.

While these initiatives show promise, there are still challenges to be addressed in further maximizing the impact of Islamic banking on reducing social disparities. Additionally, to obtain more comprehensive and concrete results, future research should involve a comparative analysis with conventional banks. This comparison would provide valuable insights into whether Islamic banking truly delivers greater social benefits compared to conventional banking, or if similar outcomes can be achieved through both systems. Such analysis would help refine our understanding of the role Islamic banking plays in fostering social equity and economic inclusion.

Moreover, it is important to note that no conventional bank in Bosnia and Herzegovina has organized an event as impactful and far-reaching as the Sarajevo Business Forum. This annual conference, spearheaded by BBI, has positioned the bank as a leader not only in the financial sector but also in promoting international investment and economic development in the country. BBI's pioneering role in creating a platform for global investors and local businesses further underscores its unique contribution to the region, setting it apart from conventional financial institutions.

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